

METHODS OF TREATMENT TO REDUCE INTRAOCULAR PRESSURE IN OPEN-ANGLE GLAUCOMA

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Annotation. Glaucoma is the leading cause of irreversible blindness worldwide, affecting over 60 million people worldwide. The disease is characterized by progressive death of retinal ganglion cells and their axons, associated with tissue remodeling in the optic nerve head (ONH). The corresponding visual field deterioration (VF) can progress in the area of the anatomical VF and retinal nerve fiber layer damage if the disease is not controlled. Glaucoma is a multifactorial disease, but its exact pathogenesis is still unclear. Although intraocular pressure (IOP) is the most important risk factor in the development and progression of glaucoma, reducing IOP does not guarantee that the disease will stop progressing. Some patients experience glaucoma progression despite low IOP maintenance.

Keywords: glaucoma, optic disc excavation, intraocular pressure

Materials and Methods. 90 patients with primary open angle glaucoma combined with hypertension were examined. Systemic hemodynamics of the patients with estimation of coefficient of variability of systolic and diastolic blood pressure as well as cerebral hemodynamics with estimation of vasomotor reactivity during stress test and parameters of ocular hemodynamics in POAG patients with various levels of BP in the dynamics of the disease have been studied.

Results: A total of 90 eyes of patients with primary open-angle glaucoma combined with hypertension, 36 males (40%) and 54 females (60%) were examined. The control group consisted of 27 eyes of healthy subjects of similar age with no ophthalmopathy. The mean age was 61.49 ± 9.58 years (33.5-87.9). The mean age of men was 60.1 ± 8.7 years and that of women was 62.11 ± 10.1 years.

The factors reaching statistical significance determining the deterioration of the MD variable in the studied sample were: age, IOP at dynamic observation, female gender, arterial hypertension. We studied systemic hemodynamics of the patients with estimation of coefficient of variability of systolic and diastolic blood pressure as well as cerebral hemodynamics with estimation of vasomotor reactivity during stress test and indexes of ophthalmodynamics in POAG

patients with various levels of BP in the dynamics of the disease. Glaucoma was diagnosed on the basis of characteristic changes in DZN detected by ophthalmoscopy (abnormal deviation of neural rim proportions, glaucoma EDZN, peripapillary atrophy, wedge-shaped defects in retinal nerve fiber layer adjacent to DZN margin, hemorrhages along DZN margin). Various classes of substances are available for topical application to reduce intraocular pressure. They differ in mechanism of action, degree of intraocular pressure reduction, dosage, side effects and cost. First-line topical medications have been shown to reduce intraocular pressure the most by prostaglandin analogues (bimatoprost at 5.61 mmHg, latanoprost at 4.85 mmHg, travoprost at 4.83 mmHg, and tafluprost at 4.37 mmHg), followed by beta-blockers (levobunolol at 4.51 mmHg, timolol 3.70 mmHg, carteolol 3.44 mmHg, levobetaxolol 2.56 mmHg, betaxolol 2.24 mmHg), alpha 2-adrenomimetics (brimonidine 3.59 mmHg, apraclonidine 2.52 mmHg) and carbohydrate inhibitors (dorzolamide 2.49 mmHg, brinzolamide 2.42 mmHg).

Conclusions: Prostaglandin analogues are usually prescribed for initial treatment and are used once a day, in the evening. These drugs improve uveoscleral and trabecular outflow and thereby reduce intraocular pressure. Their side effects include conjunctival hyperemia, increased eyelash growth, decreased periorbital fat and increased pigmentation of the iris and periocular skin. Systemic conditions limiting the use of prostaglandin analogues include bronchial asthma, severe cardiovascular disease and liver or kidney disease.

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